

Artemis Accords and Private Space Firms: Common Heritage Perspective

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Abstract

Initiated by NASA, the Artemis Accords were introduced in 2020 as a framework for space cooperation, aiming to offer a new model for the utilization of extraterrestrial resources. The Accords seek to strike a balance between technological advancement, private sector participation, and the principles of international law, while relying on the foundational norms of the 1967 Outer Space Treaty. Although currently considered a non-binding instrument, the Artemis Accords have the potential to evolve into a binding framework and may, in the future, influence or even challenge traditional concepts such as the principle of the "common heritage of humankind." This article, through a descriptive-analytical method, examines the extent to which the Artemis Accords align with or diverge from the existing legal regime governing outer space, particularly the 1979 Moon Agreement. The objective is to analyze the legal and conceptual implications of this new framework on the fundamental principles of international space law, with a special focus on the principle of the common heritage of humankind.

Key words: Artemis Accords, Outer Space Law, Common Heritage of Humankind, Moon Agreement, Private Space Companies, Space Resource Governance

1. Introduction

The concept of "common heritage of humankind" has gained significant prominence in international law, particularly with regard to space exploration. As humanity expands the boundaries of space, the fair utilization of extraterrestrial resources becomes increasingly important. In this context, agreements such as the Artemis Accords have been established to address new challenges, and their implementation sets the stage for a greater focus on the principle of common heritage in space. The Artemis Accords, as a framework that appears to be both bilateral and multilateral, not only highlights the evolving nature of certain concepts but also gradually transforms space management, presenting a new model for international cooperation that may even influence the principles of international law.

Adopted in 1979, the UN Treaty known as the "Moon Agreement" states that the "moon and its natural resources are the common heritage of mankind." [1] The Moon Agreement, intended as a supplement to the OST, goes a step further in declaring the Moon and other celestial bodies to be the "common heritage of mankind." [2] However, the Moon Agreement has not been widely ratified, with major spacefaring nations such as the United States, Russia, and China notably absent from the list of signatories. [3] UNCLOS III agreed with these smaller nations and established the sea as "the common heritage of mankind," and therefore states could not "claim or exercise sovereignty or sovereign rights over any part of the Area or its resources." [4] Therefore, the exploration and use of outer space should be carried out by considering the benefit and interest of all countries, as outer space is the 'province of all mankind [5].

The aim of this study is to highlight the importance of a direct and precise examination of the impact of the Artemis Accords on the fundamental principles of international law, with particular emphasis on the principle of the common heritage of humankind. This article seeks to analyze the extent to which the Artemis Accords align with or diverge from the existing legal regime governing outer space and the Moon Agreement. The research methodology is descriptive and analytical, based on international legal instruments and relevant legal opinions. In the following sections of the article, the legal foundations of the principle of the common heritage of humankind, as well as the content and implications of the Artemis Accords, will be comparatively analyzed with reference to the Outer Space Treaty and the Moon Agreement.

1. Outer Space Treaty (1967)

Considering the precedence of the 1967 Treaty and regardless of the preliminary events in the United Nations General Assembly, the principles of space law have undergone a conceptual development. Based on the framework of this article, we begin our analysis with the Outer Space Treaty and celestial bodies.

Article I, with its declaration that space, the moon, and other celestial bodies “shall be the province of all mankind”. [6] The most significant provisions of the Treaty are Articles I and II. Because of their importance to the discussion of resource appropriation in space, they are quoted here in their entirety: [7]

Article I: The exploration and use of outer space, including the moon and other celestial bodies, shall be carried out for the benefit and in the interests of all countries, irrespective of their degree of economic or scientific development, and shall be the province of all mankind. Outer space, including the moon and other celestial bodies, shall be free for exploration and use by all States without discrimination of any kind, on a basis of equality and in accordance with international law, and there shall be free access to all areas of celestial bodies. There shall be freedom of scientific investigation in outer space, including the moon and other celestial bodies, and States shall facilitate and encourage international co- operation in such investigation.

Article II: Outer space, including the moon and other celestial bodies, is not subject to national appropriation by claim of sovereignty, by means of use or occupation, or by any other means. [8]

The phrase “not subject to national appropriation” in Article II is commonly referred to as the non-appropriation principle. It is the most important phrase in the Treaty for the purposes of this Note, as will become apparent throughout the ensuing discussion. [7]

When the Outer Space Treaty was originally drafted, Article II’s non appropriation clause was generally not considered ambiguous either in terms of which actors or what parts of outer space were encompassed therein. The Cold War sensibility that spurred the establishment of the Treaty and the realities of space exploration at the time, along with concrete written evidence in the Treaty’s travaux préparatoires and the contemporaneous works of legal scholars, combine to support the conclusion that the non-appropriation principle was originally construed broadly under customary international law.[7] In a letter to the Chairman of the Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space dated June 16, 1966, Arthur Goldberg, the Permanent Representative of the United States, summarized the key points for inclusion in the eventual Outer Space Treaty. Specifically, he included as point two in his letter that “[c]elestial bodies should not be subject to any claim of sovereignty.” [9] Later in the letter, when proposing draft language for the treaty itself, Goldberg incorporated this key point into a proposed treaty provision that read: “Celestial bodies are free for exploration and use by all States . . .” [9] The very broad “any claim of sovereignty” point was satisfied, in Goldberg’s view, by referring to States in the language of the Treaty. Had he thought that entities other than States might become involved with the exploration and use of outer space, the draft language he proposed likely would have been broader to conform to the underlying key point he described as foundational to the Treaty. [7]

The current approach of the United States toward space law strategy brings renewed focus to Arthur Goldberg's 1966 perspective. This gives rise to the important question of whether the previously asserted principle of non-appropriation of celestial bodies has remained unchanged, or whether this principle has undergone a transformation in meaning or application.

Stephen Gorove was one of the few legal scholars of the late 1960s who, rather prophetically, noted that the non-appropriation principle was not as unambiguous as its drafters may have assumed. He understood the drafting of Article II of the Outer Space Treaty as founded on several assumptions: that only States would seek to appropriate space resources; and that the phrase "the moon and other celestial bodies" would be interpreted as the entire celestial body, including extracted resources such as mined minerals. [10]

Since the terms "appropriation" and "celestial bodies" in the 1967 Treaty gave rise to ambiguities, they led to legal disagreements. From a narrow interpretative perspective, "appropriation" is limited to the prohibition of sovereignty claims, whereas a broader interpretation considers economic exploitation as a form of appropriation. Moreover, it remains unclear whether extracted resources still constitute part of the celestial body. Such ambiguities have thus triggered subsequent interpretative disputes among states and private companies, playing a significant role in the adoption of national laws, such as the 2015 U.S. law and the similar legislation in Luxembourg, allowing private exploitation of space resources.

The Common Heritage principle has been interpreted differently among states. Developing states tend to hold that since common areas belong to 'all nations', any benefit derived from exploitation of such common resource should be shared equally among states, regardless of their respective contribution to the particular exploitation.²¹⁶ Under this interpretation, nations would derive benefit from exploitative activities without making either a financial or intellectual investment. On the other hand, developed countries consider reference to equitable sharing extends only to mean that every state has an equal right to exploit natural resources freely, such that states have no legitimate claim to the technology or investment in other's exploitation. [11]

To explain the concept of the "province of all mankind" in the 1967 Treaty, one author, referring to Gorove's (1972) view, writes:

It is the author's belief that at the time of the negotiation and conclusion of the Outer Space Treaty the general understanding of the term province of all mankind was to ensure that information and research i.e., the benefits, from the use and exploration of outer space and the celestial bodies would be shared equally with all states and the public at large. This concept can be found in Roman law as *res communis omnium*, meaning that states and individuals would be entitled to these benefits. Stephen Gorove makes a point to state that he was under the belief

that the term common heritage of all mankind is excluded from this concept and falls into a state only category of res communis humanization. [12]

It appears that the concept of "province of all mankind" in the drafting of the 1967 Outer Space Treaty was initially understood primarily in terms of scientific and public benefit. Over time, however, the involvement of private entities in space activities has led to a reinterpretation of these original definitions. In particular, distinctions and interpretive differences have emerged between the concepts of res communis omnium and the common heritage of mankind. This shift paved the way for domestic legislation in the United States and Luxembourg that aggressively moved toward the recognition of private ownership and exploitation of space resources. In other words, traditional interpretations of the principles of international space law are now undergoing semantic and practical transformation, necessitating in-depth examination and reconsideration.

2. Moon Agreement (1979)

In this section of the article, the Moon Agreement is examined. Although this agreement defines and elaborates the concept of the common heritage of mankind with more precision and detail than the Outer Space Treaty, it was not embraced by the major space powers. On the other hand, while a few years later the concept of the common heritage of mankind was recognized and developed as a successful legal regime in the deep seabed and maritime areas under the 1982 United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, the Moon Agreement was marginalized due to its lack of broad acceptance.

While some scholars therefore view 'province of all mankind' and 'common heritage of mankind' as equivalent and interchangeable terms. [8] In response to these concerns, the UN passed the Agreement Relating to the Implementation of Part XI of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, which recognized preexisting claims to ocean mining sites and implemented a "market oriented approach" to "managing seabed resources." [13]

Unfortunately, the Outer Space Treaty's drafters chose not to define the key term "benefit," leaving it unclear whether or not "benefit" could include economic benefits, environmental benefits (for example, reduced mining-generated pollution from tailings basins, acid drainage, or erosion), or any other beneficial outcomes. This section has resulted in further dispute about whether the common heritage principle precludes private property ownership. [14]

In other words, the successful experience of the 1982 United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea can be considered as influenced by prior legal developments and events. While the 1967 Outer Space Treaty was drafted under the excitement and fascination of early space exploration and focused mainly on general principles, Article 6 subtly yet deliberately acknowledged a limited

role for private actors. Following the first human landing on the Moon, economic interests gradually entered the domain of space law—separate from the military competition of the Cold War era. However, investors, especially given the significant role of the private sector in maritime transportation, increasingly turned their attention to the field of the law of the sea. As a result, “profit” and economic exploitation became central concerns for developing countries during the drafting of the Law of the Sea Convention, more so than during the negotiations of the Moon Agreement. It may be said that the sea was perceived as a concrete and tangible example of shared resources, while the Moon and celestial bodies, due to their abstract and distant nature, appeared more symbolic and conceptual leading to caution and practical reluctance in adopting a similar legal regime for them.

The ‘common heritage of mankind’ principle in the Moon Agreement (hereafter ‘the Common Heritage principle’) guarantees that outer space and its resources are a common heritage. However, the Common Heritage principle, while providing for equal freedom of access, also requires the exploiter to share any benefit with all states. But what is the implication of this principle on intellectual property rights? A significant quantity of legal scholarship is devoted to the dominant role which the Common Heritage principle plays in space activities. Thus, it is appropriate to take account of the Common Heritage principle when considering the international law implications of any utilization of outer space and space resources, including the Moon. The Common Heritage principle of the Moon Agreement shares some common characteristic with the Province of humankind principle in terms of free access on an equal basis, but differs from the latter in some aspects. The Common Heritage principle has been interpreted to mean that the protected areas and their natural resources form a human heritage, such that the interest of future generation must be taken into account when these common areas are being exploited. It prohibits any one state or person from exclusively using these areas or their resources. Thus, a sharing of benefit arises from exploitative activities in these protected areas, in accordance with principles and rules established by an international regime. [15]

The Space Treaty Institute (www.spacetreaty.org) has been working on such a legal framework since 2016. After much drafting, consultation, and revision, it has produced a resource utilization/management agreement that satisfies the requirements of Article II of the OST and Article 11 of the Moon Treaty. It is based on three organizational principles:

- 1) The Agreement must support all public and private activity;
- 2) It must protect essential public policies;
- 3) It must integrate and build upon current institutions and processes. [16]

The Moon Treaty provides the international authority to manage resource utilization. Article 11 does not prohibit resource utilization; it just prohibits any one country or group of countries from imposing their exclusive regime on others: [16]

11.1. The moon and its natural resources are the common heritage of mankind, which finds its expression in the provisions of this Agreement, in particular in paragraph 5 of this article. 11.2. The moon is not subject to national appropriation by any claim of sovereignty, by means of use or occupation, or by any other means.

11.3. Neither the surface nor the subsurface of the moon, nor any part thereof or natural resources in place, shall become property of any State, international intergovernmental or non-governmental organization, national organization or non-governmental entity or of any natural person. The placement of personnel, space vehicles, equipment, facilities, stations and installations on or below the surface of the moon, including structures connected with its surface or subsurface, shall not create a right of ownership over the surface or the subsurface of the moon or any areas thereof. The foregoing provisions are without prejudice to the international regime referred to in paragraph 5 of this article . . .11.5. States Parties to this Agreement hereby undertake to establish an international regime, including appropriate procedures, to govern the exploitation of the natural resources of the moon as such exploitation is about to become feasible.” [17]

One of the main reasons for the non-membership of major spacefaring countries in the Moon Agreement was its excessive focus on the details of the extraction and utilization of the lunar surface and subsurface. The Agreement seemed to primarily address the concerns of less developed and developing countries, containing provisions that still hold special significance for the concept of the common heritage of mankind today. However, advanced spacefaring countries, viewing lunar exploitation as an achievable goal, realized earlier the limitations related to benefits and sovereignty, and therefore, although they participated in the drafting process, they refrained from becoming members. Interestingly, the Moon Agreement was not welcomed by many developing countries either. This may even indicate a lack of genuine willingness to strengthen the concept of the common heritage of mankind. Consequently, both countries of the North and the South practically weakened the Agreement, paving the way for the emergence of the Artemis Accords.

3. Artemis Accord (2020)

In this section of the article, the content of the Artemis Accords is examined. The main objective is to analyze the approach of this agreement regarding the principle of the common heritage of

humankind and to compare it with the perspectives of the Outer Space Treaty and the Moon Agreement.

Artemis is a NASA program in cooperation with private companies and space agencies, including the European one, for the development of manned space flights. This program was named after the eponymous U.S. lunar exploration program. The main objectives of such a program are to establish and implement a form of basic principles of research and economic activity in outer space, implement the provisions of the Outer Space Treaty and other relevant international instruments and thereby establish a political understanding regarding mutually beneficial practices for future exploration and use of outer space, with a focus on activities conducted in support of the Artemis Program. The program operates based on agreements on the principles of cooperation in public research and the use of the Moon, Mars, comets, and asteroids for peaceful purposes. The Artemis Accords are part of the Artemis Program led by the U.S. National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA). A distinctive trait of the Artemis Program is that it envisages the construction of a permanent outpost on the Moon, which includes a dedicated orbital station (the lunar “Gateway”) and a self-sustaining lunar base (the Moon Base Camp). To implement the Artemis Program, NASA is seeking the international collaboration of States and commercial partners. To that intention, it has elaborated a set of guidelines that will form an integral part of any subsequent agreement with international partners. In practice, states wishing to enter into collaboration with NASA must commit in advance to abide by the principles outlined in the Artemis Accords. [17]

The depository of all four documents is the U.N. However, in the case of the Artemis Agreement, the United States, as the depository, will keep the original texts of the agreements, verify that all signatures, documents, and notices related to the Agreement are in order, and inform the states that have the right to become parties to the Agreement. [18]

The issue of space resources is highlighted in Section 10(Artemis Accords). Vladymir Tolstykh has noted that in the past few years, the situation related to the exploration and use of space had changed dramatically and it had been proven that the extraction of space resources could be profitable; there was a gap between the state of the space industry in the United States and other countries. These changes resulted in a US-initiated reform aimed at legalizing the appropriation of extracted space resources, as well as, in the long term, at legalizing the appropriation of sites of celestial bodies and resources in situ by both individuals and states. Its instruments are proposals for the reinterpretation of key agreements, new U.S. and Luxembourg law and the Artemis Accords signed on 13 October 2020. As a result, we can talk about the emergence of an international custom that legalizes the appropriation of extracted resources.[19]

Per the Artemis Accords, the signatories note that the use of space resources can benefit humanity by providing critical support for safe and sustainable operations. The Signatories

emphasize that the extraction and use of space resources, including any recovery from the surface or underground surface of the Moon, Mars, comets, or asteroids, should be carried out in a manner consistent with the Outer Space Treaty and support of safe and sustainable space activities. The Signatories affirm that the extraction of space resources does not inherently constitute national appropriation under Article II of the Outer Space Treaty and that contracts and other legal instruments relating to space resources should be consistent with that Treaty. The Signatories commit to informing the Secretary-General of the United Nations as well as the public and international scientific community of their space resource extraction activities per the Outer Space Treaty. The Signatories intend to use their experience under the Accords to contribute to multilateral efforts to further develop international practices and rules applicable to the extraction and utilization of space resources, including through ongoing efforts at the COPUOS. Interestingly, neither the Artemis Agreement nor the Outer Space Treaty contains direct prohibitions on the establishment of ownership of space resources. This means that the general recognition by all signatories of the legality of exploitation and subsequent recognition of the right of ownership of space resources is a kind of legal precondition for participation in the Artemis Program. It is noteworthy that the three signatory states to the Agreement have settled in advance the issue of commercial extraction of minerals on celestial bodies. ... the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies (Agreement, 1979). St. Article 11 of this Agreement establishes that the Moon and its natural resources are the common heritage of mankind and that the Moon's subsoil, parts of its surface or subsoil or natural resources, where they are located, may not be owned by any State, international intergovernmental or non-governmental organization, national organization or non-governmental institution or any individual. [18]

An important point based on international space law instruments is the following: according to the provisions of the Artemis Accords, the signatory parties do not consider the extraction of space resources to be in violation of the principle of non-appropriation as stated in Article II of the 1967 Outer Space Treaty. They are thus moving toward the formation of a new international custom regarding the appropriation of space resources. On the other hand, another key document in international space law—Article 11 of the 1979 Moon Agreement—explicitly prohibits any form of state or private ownership not expressly permitted under the Agreement. Moreover, and more importantly, the Moon's resources are declared to be the common heritage of mankind.

In our opinion, the advantage of the Artemis agreement is the spread beyond the United States of the already successful scenario of public-private partnership in space activities, promoting the commercialization of such activities by involving international partners and private entities. It is the United States that is responsible for building new diplomatic bridges between the states that have been engaged in space activities only recently, as well as those states that have previously had no precedent for interaction with each other in the space sector. The signing of the Artemis

Agreement is important for the signatory countries due to further cooperation in the study and use of outer space for peaceful purposes.[18]

If the United States' participation in the adoption of the National Space Law of 2015 is considered a foundation for broad cooperation with the private sector, it can be said that this policy has accelerated the development of space technologies. The reason lies in the greater agility and flexibility of the private sector compared to governmental agencies such as NASA. This approach had already contributed to the advancement of U.S. business models in other economic sectors. Accordingly, in the context of the Artemis Accords, it seems that granting broader authority to private actors goes beyond mere technological development and lays the groundwork for a new space race—this time between private players and even other states, all within the strategic framework of Artemis, aiming at the exploration and exploitation of space resources. This stands in contrast to the Moon Agreement, which conditioned the exploitation of celestial bodies' natural resources on the establishment of an international mechanism and legal regime—something that, although envisioned, has never materialized. From this perspective, the Artemis Accords can be seen as an agreement that effectively disregards the Moon Agreement.

The Artemis Accords are not binding in nature, but the overriding goal is to ensure top priorities in space activities. The Artemis Accords took into account the obligations of the Outer Space Treaty, as it is an international basis for cooperation. It should be noted that the Artemis Accords provide a starting point for further discussion of the international framework for space activities, as they encourage and facilitate the fulfillment of space commitments. Important in the study of Artemis agreements is that they are fully developing the principle of adaptive governance, which is extremely important today for international cooperation. The issue of space exploitation is becoming important today, and this process is gaining in importance and becoming inevitable, contrary to the provisions of the Moon Agreement of 1979. Therefore, provisions of the Artemis Accords are innovative, moving towards development issues of space resources exploitation, but need further improvement. [18]

In 2020, The United States launched the Artemis Accords. [19] It, like the Moon Agreement and Outer Space Treaty, calls for the peaceful use of outer space. [19]

The repeated emphasis on peaceful purposes in the Artemis Accords initially creates the general impression that this document does not conflict with established instruments of international space law. However, a content-based analysis reveals that Artemis adopts a selective and partial approach toward the existing legal framework. In other words, the agreement seeks to present itself as a complementary model, yet in practice, it functions as a substitute for current international instruments. From this perspective, Artemis can be regarded as an attempt to redefine the fundamental concepts of the Moon Agreement, particularly the principle of the Common Heritage of Mankind. Rather than adhering to existing, sometimes binding rules, it

offers a pragmatic interpretation aligned with the interests of leading nations and private companies. Such an approach could gradually undermine the principles of international solidarity and pave the way for exceptionalist practices in the exploitation of space resources.

4. Comparative Analysis

In this section of the article, the content of the Artemis Accords is examined in a more specific and in-depth manner. The main objective is to analyze the approach of these accords toward the principle of the common heritage of mankind and to compare it with the perspectives of the Outer Space Treaty and the Moon Agreement, in a way that goes beyond the case-based analyses presented in previous sections.

"Some authors have explained the Artemis Accords as follows:" Any effort by another party to access resources in the unilaterally declared zone is deemed to be "harmful interference" and a violation of Article IX of the OST. Exclusion by any other name, including safety, is still exclusion, and exclusion is appropriation, which is specifically prohibited by Article II of the OST. [16] Therefore, Section 11 of the Artemis Accords, as currently written, violates the Outer Space Treaty. The pronouncements in Section 11, and throughout the Accords, that they are intended to comply with the Outer Space Treaty are not enough to negate the exclusionary nature of the "safety" zones. [16]

What is defined in international law as "creeping expropriation" refers to actions by certain states against foreign investors. Such actions typically occur within the territorial jurisdiction of the expropriating state. However, on celestial bodies such as the Moon, where the concept of state territory and sovereignty is fundamentally different, the owners of equipment installed or stationed on the surface may engage in acts of occupation and appropriation through the establishment of so-called "safety zones." These acts are commonly referred to as "hidden appropriation," which, in any case, constitute a violation of the fundamental principles of international space law as enshrined in Article II of the 1967 Outer Space Treaty. Therefore, from a documentary and legal standpoint, the Artemis Accords offer a unilateral interpretation of space law principles.

Although the OST prohibits exclusion, it does not prohibit the acquisition and/or use of outer space would not be a problem. Outer space would be considered a non-exclusive, non-subtractable public resource, a true public commons. But there are practical limits to the amount of space resources that can be accessed, primarily due to limits in current Earth technology. Although outer space is de jure nonexcludable, it is nevertheless de facto subtractable, and thus a common-pool resource with the potential for conflict. [16]

If we are to examine legal events in outer space from a realist perspective, we are confronted with a set of justifications in the style of international law that appear within the framework of space law. While the non-exclusive and non-appropriable nature of outer space may be regarded as a *de jure* legal principle, in practice we are faced with states and private entities from technologically advanced spacefaring nations that, by virtue of their superior technology, engage in the extraction of publicly accessible space resources. This conduct, in effect, suggests a kind of *de facto* appropriation.

For the sake of exposition, the provisions of the Artemis Accords can be grouped into three categories. The first category simply transposes provisions of the Outer Space Treaty into the text of the Artemis Accords. The second category implements provisions of the Outer Space Treaty, adding detail and clarity to the rights and obligations contained therein. The third category introduces new concepts. The explicit commitment of the signatories to operate within the boundaries of the Outer Space Treaty's principles makes the content of the Artemis Accords relatively uncontentious. However, closer scrutiny reveals that certain provisions of the Artemis Accords go a step further than mere implementation, effectively introducing concepts and principles not mentioned in the Outer Space Treaty, thus raising issues of compatibility. [17]

In other words, what is observed in the Artemis Accords appears, on the surface, to be a continuation of the Outer Space Treaty, bypassing the Moon Agreement, and expanding the 1967 foundational framework through a redefinition of the fundamental concepts of appropriation and possession. In this sense, the principle of the common heritage of humankind and the development of international space law are caught in a conceptual tug-of-war.

The CH principle has been seen by literature as an evolution of the *res communis omnium* concept.¹¹ However, unlike this concept, the CH principle does not confer the right to freely use and exploit a common area. Rather, it limits use and exploitation by mandating that any exploitation must be conducted according to rules established by the international community as a whole. [20]

These stark differences are most apparent when it comes to the issue of space resource extraction and utilization. Section 10(3) of the Accords provides that: [21]

“The Signatories commit to informing the Secretary-General of the United Nations as well as the public and the international scientific community of their space resource extraction activities in accordance with the Outer Space Treaty.”

Article 10(3) of the Artemis Agreement attempts to regulate extraction and utilization activities by reporting them to the UN Secretary-General and the broader scientific community within the framework of the 1967 Outer Space Treaty. However, this practice does not precisely follow the Treaty but is carried out through Artemis's unique model. Essentially, it seems that Artemis seeks

to revert to the pre-Outer Space Treaty era, when space activities were limited to scientific announcements and international legal obligations were still in their infancy. This return appears to grant greater freedom of action to the Artemis parties.

Section 10(4) then provides that: [21] “The Signatories intend to use their experience under the Accords to contribute to multilateral efforts to further develop international practices and rules applicable to the extraction and utilization of space resources, including through ongoing efforts at the COPUOS.”

Article 10(3) of the Artemis Agreement attempts to regulate extraction and utilization activities by reporting them to the UN Secretary-General and the broader scientific community within the framework of the 1967 Outer Space Treaty. However, this practice does not precisely follow the Treaty but is carried out through Artemis's unique model. Essentially, it seems that Artemis seeks to revert to the pre-Outer Space Treaty era, when space activities were limited to scientific announcements and international legal obligations were still in their infancy. This return appears to grant greater freedom of action to the Artemis parties.

establish an international régime (...) to govern exploitation of the natural resources of the [M]oon as such exploitation is about to become feasible.” Clearly, this was a touch ambitious - plans for lunar resource exploitation abound, but actual exploitation has not yet taken place. One of the purposes of this dedicated “international régime” is to ensure resources are shared equitably. It is noteworthy in this regard that the Moon Agreement speaks of “equitable sharing” rather than “equal sharing”: to this end, special consideration is to be given to those countries that have contributed directly, or indirectly, to the exploration of the Moon. [21] These provisions appear innocuous, but they confirm that the Signatories intend to extract space resources before any further international practices or rules develop regarding such extraction. This appears to differ from the process envisioned in Article 11(5) of the Moon Agreement, which can be read as requiring that the “international régime” be established before space resource extraction takes place. [21]

The revival of debates on equitable distribution versus equal distribution evokes John Rawls' theory of distributive justice. Rawls emphasized equality of opportunity and argued that inequalities in distribution are only justifiable if they benefit the least advantaged. This perspective can also be linked to the concept of spatial justice, particularly within the framework of the 1967 Outer Space Treaty, which recognizes outer space as the “province of all mankind,” and the Moon Agreement, which introduced the principle of the “common heritage of mankind.” Accordingly, the rights of non-spacefaring and less-developed spacefaring nations in relation to space resources cannot be overlooked. Therefore, the Artemis Accords require careful legal analysis and a reconsideration of distributive principles in international space law—especially

with regard to the establishment of regimes that ensure the benefits derived from space resources are shared equitably, though not necessarily equally, among all states.

Despite such differences, it is important to keep in mind that the Accords are not a treaty. Rather, they are a non-binding, political commitment that operationalizes the bedrock of international space law, the Outer Space Treaty. As such, comparing and contrasting the Accords with the Moon Agreement is not a strict like-for-like comparison. [21]

It should not be overlooked that what ultimately generates international legal effects is the actual conduct and practice of space resource exploitation, rather than merely the titles or the legal nature of existing instruments. Therefore, although the Artemis Accords are currently considered non-binding and categorized as political commitments, their significance cannot be diminished. Once the practical exploitation of space resources begins, these non-binding instruments may serve as a basis for asserting priority over more accessible resources—potentially leading, in practice, to the formation of binding customary norms.

5. Conclusion

However, non-binding instruments are often a stepping stone for the development of binding instruments. This is exactly what happened in the early days of international space law: a non-binding resolution adopted by the General Assembly in 1963 formed the basis for the Outer Space Treaty, with some provisions carried over verbatim. It is not impossible to imagine the same thing happening with the Accords, with a binding, multilateral treaty being the end result. Given this trajectory, perhaps the time has come to end the debate, cut the final threads, and close the book on the Moon Agreement once and for all. [21]

The Artemis Agreement attempts to provide a new framework for the exploitation of space resources that remains within the principles of the 1967 Outer Space Treaty, while at the same time offering a more practical and realistic model in light of current technological advancements and the role of private actors. On one hand, Artemis seeks legitimacy based on international legal principles by placing activities, for now, within a framework of notification to the UN Secretary-General and scientific and public bodies. On the other hand, in practice, it appears that this agreement, by redefining concepts of ownership and appropriation, is effectively creating new conditions that differ from the classical interpretation of the 1967

Treaty and could lead to the emergence of a kind of "hidden ownership" over space resources.

This situation reflects a conceptual tension between preserving the common heritage of mankind as a fundamental principle and the desire for economic and political exploitation of space resources by developed countries and private commercial space companies. In other words, Artemis seeks to realistically and based on current technological conditions and international politics, define new rules for space law that may soon give rise to legal and ethical challenges. Ultimately, these discussions indicate that international space law is evolving and requires further efforts to achieve a sustainable balance between national interests, the common interests of humanity, and international legal obligations.

By examining the text of the Moon Agreement and new trends in international space law, it becomes clear that despite the treaty's anticipation of establishing an international regime before resource exploitation, in practice, resource extraction has been pre-empted and new agreements like Artemis provide innovative and sometimes differing frameworks from the original treaty. The concept of equitable resource sharing, rather than equal sharing, gives special attention to countries participating in exploration, which can impact the principle of the common heritage of mankind. These developments, while demonstrating the dynamism of space law and the potential transformation of non-binding agreements into binding treaties, mark the beginning of a new era in space resource governance. Nevertheless, significant legal and political challenges remain, requiring broader and more effective international agreements and rules.

Given these developments and the growing trend of private and governmental space activities, it is time for the issues related to the Moon Agreement and other old accords to be reviewed so that, in line with new technologies, a fresh and more efficient legal framework based on new realities is formed. Ultimately, to protect the rights of both developed and less-developed countries, uphold principles of distributive justice and the common heritage of mankind, and prevent imminent potential injustices, the international community must urgently work towards

drafting a comprehensive, binding, and fair legal regime, as repeatedly emphasized by legal scholars in the field of space resource exploitation.

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